

Caffeine-derived 8- α -methylthioglycolic acid compounds as promising neuroprotective agents in cellular models of neurotoxicity

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Abstract

The effects of a series of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives (Jas 1–Jas 10), possessing potential applicability in neurodegenerative diseases, were investigated using neurotoxicity models based on the human neuroblastoma cell line SH-SY5Y. These compounds contain various substituents that modify and improve the physicochemical properties of caffeine, including solubility, molecular weight, and acidity, which may influence their biological activity. The proposed mechanism of action is associated with the modulation of G protein-coupled adenosine receptors in neuronal cells. The neuroprotective potential of the compounds was evaluated in an L-glutamate (L-GLU, 60 mM, 24 h)-induced excitotoxicity model and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 5 μ M and 6 μ M, 1 h)-induced oxidative stress models. Cell viability and intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) production were analyzed using standard *in vitro* assays. The results demonstrated that the tested derivatives exhibited antioxidant and moderate neuroprotective effects in both experimental models. The most pronounced activity was observed for compound Jas 9 in the L-GLU-induced neurotoxicity model and for compound Jas 8 in the H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress model. Furthermore, Jas 8 statistically significantly reduced intracellular ROS production (+++*p* < 0.001), supporting its strong antioxidant potential. Overall, these findings indicate that the selected caffeine derivatives are promising candidates for further pharmacological and toxicological evaluation.

Keywords

Antioxidants, caffeine derivatives, excitotoxicity, hydrogen peroxide, L-glutamate, neuroprotection, oxidative stress, SH-SY5Y cells

Introduction

Xanthines are a class of biologically active, plant-derived compounds belonging to purine alkaloids (Zandavar and Babazad 2023). The principal naturally occurring xanthine derivatives include caffeine, theobromine, and theophylline, which differ in their physicochemical and pharmacological properties. These compounds are widely distributed in commonly consumed plant sources such as Semen Colae,

Semen Coffeae, Semen Cacao, Folium Theae, and Pasta Guarana (Emerson and Chappel 1999). Due to their broad availability and diverse biological activities, xanthines have long been the subject of extensive pharmacological and toxicological research, with increasing interest in their potential therapeutic applications (Yadav et al. 2022).

Among xanthine derivatives, caffeine is the most extensively consumed and studied compound worldwide. It readily crosses the blood–brain barrier and exerts pronounced

effects on the central nervous system, including increased alertness, reduced fatigue, and improved cognitive and motor performance (Garrett and Griffiths 1997). Caffeine acts as a non-selective antagonist of adenosine A_2A receptors and is widely used as a central nervous system stimulant. By blocking adenosine receptors, it prevents adenosine-mediated inhibition of neuronal activity and enhances neurotransmission (Xie et al. 2007; Sharma et al. 2023). In addition, caffeine inhibits phosphodiesterase enzymes, leading to elevated intracellular cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) levels, which further amplifies its stimulatory effects (Sharma et al. 2023). Through these mechanisms, caffeine modulates multiple intracellular signaling cascades that regulate neuronal excitability, synaptic transmission, and plasticity (Yadav et al. 2022).

Beyond its well-established stimulatory properties, caffeine and related xanthines exhibit a wide spectrum of neurobiological activities that are increasingly recognized as relevant to neuroprotection. These include modulation of neurotransmitter release, attenuation of neuroinflammatory responses, and regulation of oxidative stress pathways (Ruggiero et al. 2022). Furthermore, xanthines may influence glial cell function and synaptic homeostasis, thereby contributing to the maintenance of neuronal integrity under pathological conditions (Yadav et al. 2022). Such pleiotropic effects have attracted considerable attention in the context of neurodegenerative diseases.

Neurodegenerative disorders, including Parkinson's disease (PD) and Alzheimer's disease (AD), are characterized by progressive neuronal dysfunction and loss, commonly associated with oxidative stress, protein aggregation, mitochondrial dysfunction, and neuroinflammation (Goldoni et al. 2003; Jellinger 2010). The multifactorial nature of these diseases presents substantial challenges for elucidating pathogenic mechanisms and developing effective therapeutic strategies. In this context, compounds capable of simultaneously targeting multiple pathological pathways are of particular interest, as they may offer advantages over single-target approaches.

The development of experimental models that adequately reproduce the complex pathophysiology of neurodegenerative diseases remains challenging. Nevertheless, *in vitro* models represent indispensable tools for the initial assessment of pharmacological and toxicological properties, as well as for the investigation of mechanisms of action and dose–response relationships (Jellinger 2010). Among the most widely used approaches are L-glutamate (L-GLU) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2)-induced neurotoxicity models, which mimic key features of neuronal injury and degeneration (Yadav et al. 2022).

L-GLU is the primary excitatory neurotransmitter in the central nervous system; however, excessive accumulation leads to excitotoxicity, characterized by calcium overload, oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, and subsequent neuronal cell death (Yap et al. 2020). In parallel, H_2O_2 induces oxidative damage through lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation, and DNA damage, ultimately resulting in apoptotic cell death (Yadav et al. 2022). These

models are widely employed due to their ability to simulate distinct yet interconnected mechanisms underlying neurodegeneration.

Xanthine derivatives, including caffeine, exhibit both neurostimulatory and neuroprotective effects. They act by blocking adenosine receptors, inhibiting phosphodiesterase, and modulating adenosine transport, thereby enhancing neuronal activity and demonstrating potential therapeutic relevance in neurodegenerative conditions such as AD, PD, and ischemic injury (Yadav et al. 2022). Structural modifications of caffeine, particularly substitutions at the C-8 position, may significantly alter its pharmacological profile, including receptor affinity, bioavailability, and overall biological activity, thereby providing opportunities for the development of novel therapeutic agents.

The present study aims to investigate the neuroprotective and antioxidant effects of newly synthesized derivatives of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid in *in vitro* models of L-GLU and H_2O_2 neurotoxicity, with the goal of identifying compounds with enhanced biological activity and therapeutic potential.

Materials and methods

Investigated compounds

The investigated compounds are derivatives of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid, synthesized as antioxidants with potential neuroprotective effects. They belong to different series, with the common structural feature being the presence of a xanthine ring. The compounds are coded as follows: Jas 1, Jas 2, Jas 3, Jas 4, Jas 5, Jas 6, Jas 7, Jas 8, Jas 9, and Jas 10.

Cell culture and experimental design

The human neuroblastoma cell line SH-SY5Y (Sigma-Aldrich, ECACC) was used as an *in vitro* neuronal model. Cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS), 2 mM L-glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. Cultures were maintained at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO_2 . The medium was replaced every 2–3 days to ensure optimal growth conditions. For all experimental procedures, cells were seeded in 96-well plates at appropriate densities and allowed to attach for 24 h prior to treatment. The investigated compounds (Jas 1–Jas 10) were applied at various concentrations depending on the specific assay.

Evaluation of cytotoxicity (MTT assay)

Evaluation of the cytotoxic effects of the synthesized caffeine derivatives was carried out using the MTT colorimetric method (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide), based on the protocol established by Mosmann (Mosmann 1983). SH-SY5Y cells

Figure 1. Hydrogen peroxide-induced oxidative stress model in severe injury (A) 6 μM concentration of H_2O_2 and mild injury (B) 5 μM concentration of H_2O_2 .

were exposed to the investigated compounds (Jas 1, Jas 2, Jas 3, Jas 4, Jas 5, Jas 6, Jas 7, Jas 8, Jas 9, and Jas 10) for 24 h. Following treatment, MTT solution was added and incubated to allow the formation of formazan crystals by viable cells. The resulting crystals were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically. Absorbance readings were obtained at 570 nm with background correction at 690 nm using a Synergy 2 microplate reader (BioTek Instruments, Inc., Winooski, VT, USA). All concentrations were evaluated in six independent replicates ($n = 6$), and the results were expressed as a percentage of viability compared to untreated controls. Cell viability was expressed as a percentage relative to untreated control cells.

L-GLU-induced neurotoxicity model

Cells were seeded in 96-well plates at a density of 16,000 cells per well, using only the inner 60 wells, and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO_2 . After incubation, the culture medium was removed, and the cells were pretreated with the investigated compounds at their maximum safe concentration for 30 min. Subsequently, excitotoxic injury was induced by exposure to 60 mM L-GLU in the presence or absence of the tested compounds, followed by incubation for 24 h under standard culture conditions. The neuroprotective potential of the compounds was evaluated using an L-GLU-induced excitotoxicity model. Untreated cells served as an intact control, while cells exposed only to 60 mM L-GLU were used as a damage control. Following incubation, cell viability was assessed using the MTT assay.

Hydrogen peroxide-induced oxidative stress model

The neuroprotective potential of the investigated compounds (Jas 1–Jas 10) was evaluated using modified H_2O_2 -induced oxidative stress models. Cells were preincubated with the test compounds for 2 h prior to exposure to hydrogen peroxide. After treatment, the medium was replaced with fresh culture medium, and cells were further incubated for 24 h with cell culture medium before cell viability assessment using the MTT

assay. To enable a more precise evaluation of the protective effects, two models of oxidative injury were applied (Fig. 1A, B). In the severe injury model, a higher concentration of H_2O_2 (6 μM) was used, resulting in an approximately 40–50% reduction in cell viability, whereas in the mild injury model, a lower concentration of H_2O_2 (5 μM) was applied, leading to approximately 20% cell death. These approaches allowed assessment of compound efficacy under different degrees of oxidative stress.

This experimental design allowed a comprehensive assessment of both cytotoxic and neuroprotective effects, taking into account not only the direct impact of oxidative stress but also the capacity of the investigated compounds to mitigate damage under conditions of varying severity.

Determination of intracellular ROS levels

Intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels were determined using the fluorescent probe DCFH-DA, following a modified protocol based on Wang and Joseph (Wang and Joseph 1999). SH-SY5Y cells were seeded in 96-well plates at a density of 3×10^4 cells/well and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C in a 5% CO_2 atmosphere. Cells were then treated with test compounds (0.1, 1, and 10 μM) for 2 h. Subsequently, DCFH-DA (60 μM in serum-free medium) was added, and cells were incubated for 1 h in the dark. Oxidative stress was induced by exposure to hydrogen peroxide (6 μM) for 30 min, followed by washing with PBS (Ca^{2+}/Mg^{2+}). Fluorescence was measured using a Synergy 2 microplate reader (BioTek Instruments, USA) at excitation/emission wavelengths of 485/528 nm. Each condition was tested in six replicates ($n = 6$). ROS levels were expressed as a percentage relative to hydrogen peroxide-treated controls, while untreated cells were used to define basal ROS levels.

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using GraphPad Prism software (version 8.0). Results are presented as the mean \pm SD. Statistical significance was evaluated using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by appropriate post hoc testing for multiple comparisons. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 2. Assessment of non-cytotoxic concentrations of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives. SH-SY5Y cell viability after 24 h exposure to different concentrations of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives. Even-numbered compounds (A) and odd-numbered compounds (B). Data are expressed as the mean \pm SD from three independent experiments ($n = 3$). Statistical comparisons versus untreated control were performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ vs. untreated control).

Figure 3. L-GLU-induced neurotoxicity model. SH-SY5Y cell viability following 24 h exposure to 60 mM L-GLU in the presence or absence of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives. Untreated cells served as the intact control, while L-GLU-treated cells served as the injury control. Data are expressed as the mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ vs. L-GLU).

Results

In vitro toxicological evaluation of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives in the SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cell line

Initially, non-cytotoxic concentrations of the investigated compounds were determined for use in subsequent experiments. To facilitate data interpretation, the compounds were divided into odd (Fig. 2A) and even (Fig. 2B) groups. The corresponding graphs present the effects of different concentrations of the tested compounds on cell viability, expressed as a percentage of the control.

The experimentally determined non-toxic concentrations varied among the investigated compounds; therefore, the following concentrations were selected for subsequent experiments: 0.1 μ M (Jas 1), 1 μ M (Jas 2), 50 and 100 μ M (Jas 3), 10 and 20 μ M (Jas 4), 10 and 20 μ M (Jas 5), 50 μ M (Jas 6), 50 μ M (Jas 7), 10 and 20 μ M (Jas 8), 50 and 100 μ M (Jas 9), and 100 μ M (Jas 10).

Neuroprotective properties of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives in an L-GLU-induced injury model

The neuroprotective potential of the tested caffeine derivatives was evaluated in SH-SY5Y cells in L-GLU-induced excitotoxicity (Fig. 3). Cells were pretreated for 2 h with the compounds at different concentrations prior to treatment with 60 mM L-GLU (1 h). The concentration of L-GLU was chosen based on the determined IC_{50} value to induce cellular injury. All results were normalized to the untreated control group, defined as 100% cell viability, while the L-GLU-treated group served as the positive control. Cell viability was determined using the MTT assay and quantified spectrophotometrically.

Among all investigated derivatives, only Jas 9 demonstrated a statistically significant neuroprotective effect, providing protection by approximately 7% at 50 μ M and approximately 10% at 100 μ M, compared to the L-GLU-treated group. The effect was statistically significant at both concentrations ($p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$, re-

Figure 4. Neuroprotective effect of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives in a severe injury model in SH-SY5Y cells. The results are presented as mean values \pm SD from three independent experiments ($n = 3$). All groups were statistically compared to the untreated control using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test. Statistical significance is indicated as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$ vs. H₂O₂.

spectively). The remaining compounds did not show significant effects under the applied experimental conditions. Thus, Jas 9 was identified as the only active candidate in this excitotoxicity model.

Neuroprotective properties of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives in H₂O₂-induced injury models

A. Severe cell injury model

Severe oxidative stress conditions were induced by exposing cells to 6 μ M H₂O₂ for 1 h, resulting in approximately a 50% reduction in cell viability. Under these conditions, 2 h pretreatment with Jas 2, Jas 5, Jas 6, and Jas 8 resulted in statistically significant cytoprotective effects at different concentrations. Specifically, Jas 2 provided significant protection of approximately 16% at 1 μ M and 9% at 10 μ M. Jas 5 exhibited a pronounced concentration-dependent cytoprotective effect, with 9% protection at 0.01 μ M, reaching a maximum of 18% at 0.1 μ M, while maintaining an effect of approximately 10% at 1 μ M. Jas 6 showed a moderate but statistically significant protective effect, with approximately a 9% viability increase at 10 μ M and 8% at 50 μ M. The most pronounced effect was observed for Jas 8, which conferred approximately 18% protection at 0.1 μ M. Overall, the results indicate a concentration-dependent cytoprotective activity of the tested compounds in this H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress model. Moreover, the differences in efficacy among derivatives suggest that certain compounds exert antioxidant effects within a relatively narrow concentration range.

Further, in subsequent experiments, the pretreatment duration with the tested compounds was extended from 2 h to 24 h to evaluate their protective effects under prolonged

exposure conditions. Under severe oxidative stress conditions (6 μ M H₂O₂, 1 h) combined with extended incubation (24 h), a statistically significant cytoprotective effect was observed for Jas 8 and Jas 5 at concentrations of 0.1 μ M (** $p < 0.001$) and 1 μ M ($p < 0.05$), respectively. At these concentrations, the level of protection was approximately 7%. Notably, the most pronounced cytoprotective effect was observed for Jas 8, suggesting its enhanced neuroprotective potential under prolonged pretreatment conditions. These findings indicate that extended exposure may enhance or stabilize the protective activity of certain compounds, particularly Jas 8, under conditions of sustained oxidative stress.

B. Mild cell injury model

In this experimental model, cell injury was induced using the neurotoxin hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) at a concentration of 5 μ M for 1 h, resulting in an approximately 20% reduction in cell viability. This model was designed to simulate mild oxidative stress conditions and to allow detection of more subtle neuroprotective effects of the tested compounds. Fig. 6 illustrates the effects of different concentrations of the tested compounds on the hydrogen peroxide oxidative stress model. Cell viability is expressed as a percentage relative to the untreated control. These results further support a concentration-dependent cytoprotective effect and indicate that caffeine derivatives retain efficacy even at lower levels of oxidative stress.

A statistically significant protective effect was observed for compounds Jas 2, Jas 7, Jas 8, and Jas 10 at different concentrations. Specifically, Jas 8 (0.1 μ M and 1 μ M), Jas 2 (1 μ M), and Jas 10 (10 μ M) demonstrated significant cytoprotection ($p < 0.01$). In contrast, Jas 7 (10 μ M) and Jas 2 (10 μ M) also showed statistical significance ($p < 0.01$), suggesting a weaker or more variable protective response

Figure 5. Neuroprotective effects of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives in a severe injury model with prolonged compound pretreatment (24 h) in SH-SY5Y cells. Results are presented as the mean \pm SD from three independent experiments ($n = 3$). All groups were statistically compared with the untreated control using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test. Statistical significance is indicated as * $p < 0.05$ and *** $p < 0.001$ vs. H₂O₂.

Figure 6. Neuroprotective effect of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives in a mild injury model in SH-SY5Y cells. Results are presented as mean values \pm SD from three independent experiments ($n = 3$). All groups were statistically compared to the untreated control using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test. Statistical significance is indicated as * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$ vs. H₂O₂.

at these concentrations. Among all tested compounds, Jas 8 exhibited the most pronounced effect, showing the highest level of increase in cell viability. This finding highlights its superior protective capacity even under conditions of mild oxidative injury and suggests a consistent activity profile across different stress intensities.

Quantification of oxidative stress by DCFH-DA fluorescence assay

The effects of caffeine derivatives on intracellular ROS production were evaluated in the SH-SY5Y cell line us-

ing the DCFH-DA assay. For this experiment, the compounds showing the highest cytoprotective activity in the H₂O₂-induced injury models were selected for analysis. Results were compared with an untreated control (PBS), a compound-only control, which represents the cells treated with the tested compounds in the absence of H₂O₂, and a positive control treated with hydrogen peroxide. Hydrogen peroxide was used as an inducer of oxidative stress due to its well-established cytotoxic mechanism associated with increased intracellular ROS generation. Cells were exposed to H₂O₂ for 30 min at a final concentration of 6 μ M. The results in Fig. 7 demonstrated that compound

Figure 7. Effects of Jas 5 and Jas 8 on ROS production—DCFH–DA assay (30 min, H₂O₂). Evaluation of intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) production in SH-SY5Y cells was performed using the DCFH–DA assay following a 30 min exposure period to hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 6 μM). Results are presented as mean ± SD from three independent experiments ($n = 3$). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett’s post hoc test for multiple comparisons against the untreated control group. Statistical significance is indicated as *** $p < 0.001$ vs. untreated control and ++ $p < 0.01$, +++ $p < 0.001$ vs. H₂O₂.

Jas 8 significantly reduced ROS production at concentrations of 0.1 μM (+++ $p < 0.001$), 1 μM (+++ $p < 0.001$), and 10 μM (+++ $p < 0.01$). The most pronounced decrease in fluorescence intensity was observed at 1 μM Jas 8, corresponding to an approximately 50% reduction compared to the H₂O₂-treated control. These findings suggest potential antioxidant activity of compound Jas 8.

In the next experiment, the experimental conditions were changed, and the oxidative H₂O₂ treatment was prolonged to 60 min. The effects of the compounds on intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) production were evaluated using the DCFH–DA assay. Only compounds demonstrating the highest activity in H₂O₂-induced injury models were selected for analysis. Results were compared with an untreated control (PBS), a compound-only control (cells treated with the tested compounds in the absence of H₂O₂), and a positive control treated with H₂O₂ (6 μM). As shown in Fig. 8, treatment with Jas 8 at concentrations of 0.1 μM (+++ $p < 0.001$), 1 μM (+++ $p < 0.001$), and 10 μM (+++ $p < 0.01$) resulted in a statistically significant reduction in ROS production. Compared with the 30 min exposure assay (Fig. 7), prolonged incubation with H₂O₂ and the tested compounds led to higher fluorescence intensity in the H₂O₂-treated group and a more pronounced decrease in fluorescence in compound-treated cells. The most substantial reduction in fluorescence intensity was observed with Jas 8 at 1 μM, corresponding to an approximately 70% decrease compared to the H₂O₂-treated control. These findings further support the potential antioxidant properties of the compound under conditions of prolonged oxidative stress.

Discussion

In the present study, the neuroprotective and antioxidant potential of a series of caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives (Jas 1–Jas 10) was systematically evaluated in SH-SY5Y cells using complementary *in vitro* models of neurotoxicity. The applied experimental approach enabled assessment of compound activity under both excitotoxic and oxidative stress conditions, providing a broader characterization of their pharmacological profile.

Among the tested compounds, Jas 8 consistently demonstrated the most pronounced and reproducible neuroprotective effects across oxidative stress models. Its activity was observed within a relatively narrow low micromolar concentration range, suggesting the presence of an optimal pharmacological window rather than a simple linear dose–response relationship. This pattern was maintained under both acute and prolonged exposure conditions, indicating a stable and sustained mechanism of action.

The antioxidant properties of Jas 8 were further confirmed by the significant reduction in intracellular ROS levels observed in the DCFH–DA assay. These findings support the role of oxidative stress modulation as a primary mechanism underlying the observed neuroprotection. Hydrogen peroxide is known to induce cellular damage through excessive ROS generation, leading to lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation, and mitochondrial dysfunction (Wang and Michaelis 2010; Ghosh et al. 2018; Houldsworth 2024).

In contrast, the excitotoxicity model revealed a more selective activity profile, with Jas 9 emerging as the only

Figure 8. Effects of Jas 5 and Jas 8 on ROS production—DCFH–DA assay (60 min, H₂O₂). Evaluation of intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) production in SH-SY5Y cells was performed using the DCFH–DA assay following a 60 min exposure period to hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 6 μM). Results are presented as mean ± SD from three independent experiments ($n = 3$). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett’s post hoc test for multiple comparisons against the untreated control group. Statistical significance is indicated as *** $p < 0.001$ vs. untreated control and ++ $p < 0.01$, +++ $p < 0.001$ vs. H₂O₂.

compound demonstrating statistically significant neuroprotective effects. This observation is consistent with the distinct mechanism of L-GLU-induced toxicity, which involves overactivation of glutamate receptors, calcium influx, and activation of downstream apoptotic pathways (Yap et al. 2020; AL-Nasser et al. 2022; Magdaleno Roman and González 2024). The comparatively limited efficacy of the remaining compounds in this model suggests that their protective effects are more closely associated with antioxidant activity than modulation of excitotoxic signaling.

The differential efficacy observed between the oxidative stress and excitotoxicity models highlights the importance of mechanistic specificity in the biological activity of caffeine derivatives. While hydrogen peroxide induces direct oxidative damage via ROS generation, L-GLU triggers receptor-mediated excitotoxic processes. These differences likely account for the distinct activity profiles of Jas 8 and Jas 9 and emphasize the importance of using multiple experimental models when evaluating neuroprotective agents.

From a mechanistic perspective, the investigated compounds are structurally related to caffeine and may exert their effects, at least in part, through modulation of adenosine receptors. Adenosine signaling plays a key role in regulating neuronal excitability and synaptic transmission, with A₁ and A_{2A} receptors having distinct functional roles (Liu et al. 2019). In particular, A_{2A} receptor antagonism has been associated with neuroprotective effects in neurodegenerative conditions (Merighi et al. 2021). Caffeine and its derivatives are well-established non-selective adenosine receptor antagonists, which may contribute to their observed biological activity (Sharma et al. 2023).

The role of oxidative stress in the pathogenesis of neurodegenerative diseases is well established. ROS contribute to progressive neuronal damage through multiple interconnected pathways, including mitochondrial dysfunction, protein misfolding, and lipid peroxidation (Mooli et al. 2022; Houldsworth 2024). Neurons are particularly vulnerable to oxidative damage due to their high metabolic demand and limited antioxidant defenses (Wang and Michaelis 2010). Therefore, compounds capable of effectively reducing intracellular ROS levels are of considerable therapeutic interest.

Overall, the findings of this study demonstrate that caffeine-derived compounds can exhibit distinct and mechanism-specific neuroprotective profiles depending on the experimental model applied. Jas 8, in particular, combines consistent antioxidant activity with measurable cytoprotective effects, making it a promising lead compound for further pharmacological optimization and evaluation in more advanced *in vitro* and *in vivo* models of neurodegeneration.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that caffeine-8- α -methylthioglycolic acid derivatives exert measurable neuroprotective and antioxidant effects in SH-SY5Y cells across complementary *in vitro* models of neurodegeneration. The compounds modulated cell viability under both L-GLU-induced excitotoxicity and H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress, with efficacy dependent on injury severity, exposure conditions, and concentration. Among all

tested derivatives, Jas 8 consistently showed the most robust and reproducible activity, significantly reducing intracellular ROS formation and improving cell survival under oxidative stress conditions. Jas 5 and Jas 9 also exhibited context-dependent neuroprotective effects, indicating structural and mechanistic specificity within the series. The observed activity profile suggests that neuroprotection is closely associated with antioxidant mechanisms and may be further supported by adenosine receptor antagonism, consistent with the pharmacological design of these caffeine-derived compounds. Overall, these findings identify Jas 8 as a promising lead candidate for further optimization and warrant its evaluation in more complex *in vitro* systems and *in vivo* models of neurodegeneration.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Use of commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines: Human neuroblastoma cell line SH-SY5Y (Sigma-Aldrich, ECACC) Catalog number: 94030304.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

D.S. (Denitsa Stefanova) – conceptualization and performance of toxicological experiments; investigation; experimental work; data curation; data analysis and processing; interpretation of results; visualization; writing – original draft preparation; writing – review and editing; coordination of manuscript preparation. Y.M. (Yavor Mitkov) – chemical synthesis of the compounds; preparation and characterization of chemical data; writing – review. V.T. (Virginia Tzankova) – supervision; methodological support; critical revision of the manuscript; writing – review and editing.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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